

A CHARACTERIZATION STUDY ON HIGH SPEED IMPACT DAMAGE IN CFRP LAMINATES

K. Ogi and S. Yashiro

Ehime University

3 Bunkyo-cho, Matsuyama, Ehime 790-8577, Japan

T. Okabe

Tohoku University

6-6-01, Aoba, Aramaki, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan

A. Yoshimura and T. Ogasawara

Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency

6-13-1, Osawa, Mitaka, Tokyo 181-0015, Japan

Email kogi@eng.ehime-u.ac.jp

SUMMARY

The high speed impact damage in CFRP laminates was experimentally and numerically investigated. The impact damages were observed using optical and X-Ray CT microscopy. The dynamic finite element analysis was performed to simulate the damage process introducing cohesive elements. The simulation shows good correlation with the experimental results.

Keywords: High speed impact, CFRP, Damage process, Finite element analysis, Failure criteria

INTRODUCTION

As carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been widely applied to aircraft, automobiles and other applications as light-weight materials, durability becomes more crucial for CFRP structures. Since CFRP fan blades and a CFRP fan case have already been applied to a turbo fan engine such as GE90, foreign object collision against the fan blades as well as blades collision against the fan case is one of the critical problems. Hence, it is essential to facilitate a damage process model in order to assure the durability of the CFRP fan system against foreign object damage. Most of the previous work dealt with a low speed impact with relatively mild damage, or ultra-high speed impact that causes perforation of a projectile in a CFRP target. Some experimental and numerical studies have been performed on the ballistic impact damage in carbon FRP¹⁾, glass FRP²⁾ and Kevlar FRP³⁾. However, foreign object damage due to impact within a speed range of Mach number 0.5 to 3 has not been clarified thoroughly although its damage behaviour is supposed to be complicated. The purpose of the present study is to characterize the high speed impact damage behavior in CFRP laminates used for aircraft structure. First, impact damage was introduced by collision of a flying steel sphere (projectile) to CFRP plates with the use of an electric heat gun. The surface and internal damages of the specimens were observed by using optical microscopy together with X-ray CT analysis. Then the damage process model was established on the basis of the

experimental result. Next, we performed the dynamic finite element analysis to simulate the damage process. In the analysis, cohesive elements were introduced to express the initiation and propagation of delamination while the maximum stress fracture criteria were employed to express another type of damage such as tensile, compressive and shear failure of the elements. The simulation was compared with the experimental results to understand the damage evolution mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

High speed impact tests were performed using an impact testing machine with an electroheat gun. Figure 1 shows an impact testing machine (Maruwa Electronic Incorporated) and a fixture jig of a CFRP target. A projectile set in a sabot was accelerated by high-temperature and high-pressure metal plasma, which is generated by melting and evaporation of an aluminum foil subjected to high-voltage pulse current. A steel ball with a diameter ϕ of 1.5 mm (14.2 mg) was used as a projectile. The impact speed v was roughly controlled by adjusting the applied voltage and calculated precisely through the measurement of the period of time during which the projectile travels the prescribed distance (300 mm) in a speed detector. Measured impact speed varies between 200 and 1100 m/s depending on the applied voltage and diameter of a projectile. The specimen was fixed in a square frame jig with inner width of 50 mm. Thus, this support allows bending deformation in the target during impact load.

The CFRP (carbon/epoxy, T700S/#2521R, Toray) plates with unidirectional (UD, $[0^\circ_{16}]$), cross-ply (CP, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{4S}$) and quasi-isotropic (QI, $[45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$) lamination were employed as targets. The specimens are 55 mm square and 1.6 mm thick.

The surface and the internal damages of the specimens were observed by using optical microscopy together with X-ray CT analysis. The latter can reveal the internal damage even if severe damage due to high speed impact exists on the surface.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the damage states of the front (left) and back (right) surfaces of a UD, CP and QI laminates. Some splitting cracks (A) in the fiber direction of the top ply

Fig. 1 A high-speed impact testing machine and a fixture jig of a target sample.

Fig. 2 Surface damage states of CFRP specimens.

were propagating from a crater in all the specimens. In addition, fiber breakage was observed at the tip of the crater (B) where the broken fibers were projected. Splitting cracks with finite width (C) were generated on the back surface. The effect of impact speed on surface damage modes was not identified within the speed range where the projectile did not perforate through the specimen.

Figure 3 shows X-ray photos of the (a) UD, (b) CP and (c) QI laminates after impact.

X-ray CT image of a UD specimen. Delamination as well as transverse cracking was identified as is observed in the case of low speed impact except severer damage around the crater. Figure 4 shows a detailed optical micrograph of a cross section of the impacted UD specimen. The fiber direction is normal to the picture. The laminate fractured catastrophically beneath the crater. The delamination (arrow D) was observed at almost all the interlayers. It is interesting that two kinds of transverse cracks are generated; one is closed (arrow E) and the other is open (arrow F). This is attributed to stress distribution as will be discussed later. In addition, the upheaval (circle G) was observed around the crater. The above damage evolution process was reproduced by the following numerical simulation.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

Dynamic finite element (FE) analysis was performed using a commercial FE software (ABAQUS/Explicit) which allows introduction of cohesive elements. Figure 5 depicts an FE model for a UD laminate with 16 plies. A quarter 3-dimensional model was adopted for symmetry. The 8-node solid elements were employed in addition to the 8-node cohesive elements with zero thickness that were introduced at all the interlayers. The relation between the traction force and relative displacement was assumed to be bilinear⁴⁾ and the material constants in the literature⁵⁻⁸⁾ were employed. The additional user subroutine program for the use of the maximum stress failure criteria was incorporated in the analysis to express the tensile and compressive failure in the fiber (x), transverse (y) and thickness (z) directions in addition to the shear failure in the x - y , y - z and x - z directions. The stress in the elements after tensile or shear failure was relieved and the elastic moduli were reduced to zero or 1/100 while the compressive stress in the elements continues to increase after failure. The elements were deleted when the tensile or compressive strain reaches 1.0, or the shear strain becomes 2.0. The impact speed was selected to be 250 m/s.

SIMULATION RESULTS

The maximum magnitude of the stress wave at the moment of impact was calculated to be at most 1 MPa in the thickness direction. That is why the stress wave is not supposed to affect the fracture behaviour. In the first analysis, any damage was not taken into account in order to investigate the whole tendency of the stress distribution. Figure 6 illustrates the stress distributions in the longitudinal (x) and transverse (y) directions. The top corner shows the impact point. The compressive stress exceeding the longitudinal compressive strength (1.45GPa) was generated around the impact point

Fig. 5 A quarter FE model for a UD laminate.

Fig. 6 Stress distributions in the (a) x and (b) y directions at $1.0 \mu\text{s}$ after impact. Any damage is not considered in the analysis.

Fig. 7 The damaged elements due to tensile and shear stresses on the (a) front and (b) back surfaces at $6.0 \mu\text{s}$ after impact.

(circle B) while the tensile stress larger than the transverse tensile strength (69 MPa) was observed around the impact point (circle A) as well as in the vicinity of the back surface below the impact point (circle C). This result explains that the fiber breakage due to compressive stress (arrow B in Fig. 2) and splitting or matrix cracks (arrows A and C in Fig. 2) are caused by the above stresses. Next, damage extension was considered in the analysis where failure criteria and cohesive elements were introduced.

Fig. 8 The damaged elements inside the laminate due to tensile and compressive stresses at 6.0 μ s after impact.

Figure 7 presents the damaged elements due to tensile and shear stresses on the (a) front and (b) back surfaces of the laminate at 6.0 μ s after impact. The splitting cracks (arrows A and C) on the (a) front and (b) back surfaces that correspond to the cracks denoted by arrows A and C in Fig.2 were reproduced in the analysis. Figure 8 demonstrates the damaged elements inside the laminate due to tensile and compressive stresses at 6.0 μ s after impact. The region beneath the impact point shows complicated deformation and failure. The damaged regions E and F are caused by compressive and tensile stresses,

Fig.9 Delamination region at (a) 0.5 μ s, (b) 1.0 μ s, (c) 1.5 μ s and (d) 3.0 μ s after impact.

respectively. This leads to closed and open matrix cracks denoted by arrows E and F in Fig. 4. Moreover, the upheaval is generated in the region of circle G that corresponds to the circle G in Fig. 4. This upheaval takes place as the projectile sinks into the specimen. Figure 9 shows the evolution of the delaminated region after impact. The first delamination occurs just below the impact point. Then, the delamination extends at the interface and takes place also at the under-interlayers as the projectile sinks into the laminate. The delamination tends to propagate along the fiber (x) direction rather than in the transverse (y) direction. This result agrees with the experimental result that the shape of the delamination area is a diamond as shown in Fig. 3 (a).

CONCLUSIONS

The high speed impact damage behavior in CFRP laminates was experimentally and numerically characterized. The impact damages were characterized by using optical microscopy together with X-ray CT analysis. Next, the damage evolution was reproduced by the dynamic finite element analysis where the maximum stress fracture criteria and cohesive elements were introduced. The simulation results show good correlation with the damages observed in the experiment.

References

1. Tanabe Y, Aoki M, Fujii K, Kasano H, Yasuda E. Fracture behavior of CFRPs impacted by relatively high-velocity steel sphere, *International J. Impact Eng.*, 2003; 28: 627–642.
2. He T, Wen HM, Qin Y. Finite element analysis to predict penetration and perforation of thick FRP laminates struck by projectiles, *International J. Impact Eng.*, 2008; 35: 1000–1008.
3. Gower HL, Cronin DS, Plumtree A, Ballistic impact response of laminated composite panels, *International J. Impact Eng.*, 2008; 35: 1000–1008.
4. Geubelle PH, Baylor JS. Impact-induced delamination of composites: a 2D simulation, *Compos. Part B*, 1998; 29(5): 589-602.
5. Hojo M, Ochiai S, Gsutfson CF, Tanaka K. Effect of matrix resin on delamination fatigue crack growth in CFRP laminates. *Eng. Fract. Mech.* 1994; 49(1): 35-47.
6. Hojo M, Matsuda S, Tanaka M, Ochiai S, Murakami A. Mode I delamination fatigue properties of interlayer-toughened CF/epoxy laminates. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 2006; 66(5): 665-675
7. Toray Industries. Fundamentals of carbon fiber technology and their application to Torayca products. <http://www.torayca.com/techref/>.
8. Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA). Advanced Composites Database System: JAXA-ACDB. <http://www.jaxa-acdb.com/>.